

CHARACTERIZATION OF STOCHASTIC HONEYCOMB SANDWICH FAILURE

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Abstract

Stochastic honeycombs have a complex internal architecture with missing walls and other defects, while maintaining high strength- and stiffness-to-weight ratios. Collapse mechanisms in two samples (high and low density) were investigated using x-ray tomography in a micro-CT scanner. Low aspect ratio (thickness/length) webs were found to buckle, while higher aspect ratio webs buckled and tore.

1 Introduction

Foams and honeycombs are composite materials in that they combine the properties of the base material with empty space through an internal cellular architecture. Stochastic honeycomb structures are a new type of cellular composite and a variation on the traditional plastic foam or honeycomb sandwich core material. Honeycombs are essentially two dimensional, with regular, repeatin

g unit cells, while foams have a range of cell size, web thicknesses and lengths. Stochastic honeycombs are essentially two dimensional, like honeycombs, but have web lengths and thicknesses that are variable (Fig. 1). Even in the through-thickness direction, the stochastic honeycomb webs can change in length, thickness, and orientation.

Produced in a simple, low-cost process, the out-of-plane compressive properties of polypropylene (PP) stochastic honeycombs rival that of PP honeycombs and exceed that of commercial PP foams. [1] For example, over a relative density range of 7-12% the compressive strength of stochastic honeycombs ranged from 1.0-2.5 MPa [1], while commercial honeycomb strengths ranged from 1.1-2.4 MPa. [2-5] The irregular structure of stochastic honeycombs is compensated for by the integrated face sheets, as

well as some supporting defects such as small, partial webs acting to buttress load-bearing webs.

Depending on the architecture and loading configuration, honeycombs have been shown to fail by buckling, bending, or fracture. [6,7] Analytical solutions for failure of honeycombs by elastic buckling [6], plastic collapse (bending) [7], and fracture [6] have been determined and tested experimentally. The failure mechanism has been

Fig. 1. 3D image reconstructed from a micro-CT scan, with a sample size of 40 mm × 40 mm × 15 mm (a) and the web structure as seen from the side (b), with the as-fabricated face sheets removed digitally in order to more clearly reveal the internal web structure. The scale bars are 5 mm each.

found to depend on the density of the honeycomb [6], with elastic buckling typically occurring at low densities and fracture at higher densities when the local stress exceeds the fracture stress of the material. Since honeycombs have a regular structure, the geometry of one unit cell is representative of the whole, and the same failure mechanism is generally seen throughout the structure. This is not the case for stochastic honeycombs given their complex internal architecture. Multiple failure mechanisms are expected depending on the local geometry of the webs. In addition, studies have shown that flaws or defects in a thin-walled structure (such as the webs in a stochastic honeycomb, or the walls in a conventional honeycomb) can concentrate failure at that location. [8-11] As such, we would expect that the initiation of these failure mechanisms would be triggered by local defect structures in the webs. This study is a first look at the detailed failure mechanisms in stochastic honeycombs.

2 Experimental Details

High melt strength polypropylene was heated on a metal platen in an oven at 180°C until it became a viscous melt. It was then removed from the oven and placed in a press, where another platen was pressed on top. Pressure was applied, and the upper platen was raised to the height desired for the sample (in this case, 15 mm) and locked in place. The sample spontaneously separated from the plates upon cooling, resulting in a sandwich structure that had integrated upper and lower face sheets separating a network of interconnected webs. Two samples, with relative densities of $\bar{\rho}_{LD} = 11\%$ (low density, LD) and $\bar{\rho}_{HD} = 18\%$ (high density, HD), were scanned in a Skyscan 1172 high resolution micro-CT scanner. The micro-CT scans were reconstructed into a series of cross-sections in the through-thickness direction, with voxel size of $35 \mu\text{m} \times 35 \mu\text{m} \times 35 \mu\text{m}$. The samples were then loaded in out-of-plane compression at a cross-head displacement rate of 1 mm/min to a compressive strain of 0.20, and characterized by micro-CT.

3 Results and Discussion

The detailed collapse mechanisms of the LD and HD sandwich cores were investigated by comparing micro-CT scans of individual webs before and after uniaxial compression. The starting structure of the LD and HD samples is shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 2a and

2b show mid-height cross-sectional slices. The number of webs decreased and the thickness of the webs increased as the density increased from 11% to 18%. Fig. 2c plots the cross-sectional area fraction of the stochastic honeycomb as a function of normalized through-thickness position in the sample (0 indicates the bottom of the sample, 1 indicates the top). Near both the top and bottom, the cross-sectional area fraction approaches 1 as the webs transform into the built-in skin. From Fig. 2c, it is also clear that the higher density of the HD sample is due to the greater cross-sectional area in the central 50% of the overall sandwich thickness. Over this middle half of the sample height, the area fraction of the LD sample was 0.085 ± 0.006 , while the area fraction of the HD sample was 0.114 ± 0.008 . Note that even though the cross-sectional area over the middle half of the sample is effectively constant, the web structure is constantly changing in the through-thickness direction.

Fig. 2. Micro-CT scans of the mid-height cross-sectional slice (sample size 40 mm × 40 mm × 15 mm) for the LD sample (a) and the HD sample (b). The scale bar is 5 mm and applies to both figures. The corresponding area fraction as a function of normalized position in the sample, h , from bottom to top is given in (c).

Fig. 3. Partial web in the LD as-fabricated structure. The scale bar is 2 mm.

Fig. 4. Schematic of a web bound on one side and free on the other. The length, l , height, h and thickness, t are indicated.

A fraction of the webs in the as-fabricated structure only partially span the distance between opposing face sheets, as seen in Fig. 3. While not providing a continuous load path of their own, these partial webs do still provide support to the adjacent complete webs, which are either bounded on both sides, or bounded on one side and free on the other. The three generally considered restraint conditions for thin plates are termed simply supported, built-in (or clamped), and free. [12,13] Simply supported, for a thin plate, is analogous to pin-jointed for a column or beam, and means that the plate is free to rotate around the hinge, but there is no translational displacement. In comparison, built-in edge conditions are taken to mean that there is no rotation or translation at the joint, and free is just that, the edge is unrestrained. [12,13] When modeling, the edge constraint is often chosen to be either simply supported or built-in. [14] However, in practice, this

Fig. 5. Uniaxial compression stress-strain curve for a $\bar{\rho} = 13\%$ stochastic honeycomb.

Fig. 6. Uniaxial compression stress-strain curve for LD ($\bar{\rho} = 11\%$) and HD ($\bar{\rho} = 18\%$) stochastic honeycombs to the valley (strain = 0.20).

boundary is considered to be in between the classic simply-supported and built-in boundary conditions. [6,15] A schematic of a web supported on one side with appropriate dimensions is given in Fig. 4.

The uniaxial compression stress-strain curve of stochastic honeycombs is comparable to that of conventional honeycombs with an initial peak stress due to plastic buckling, followed by a decrease towards a valley stress, followed by a final stress increase due to densification (e.g. Fig. 5 [1]). Fig. 6 illustrates stress-strain curves for the LD and HD samples of the present study, which were compressed to the valley stress beyond the initial peak and then unloaded for subsequent micro-CT characterization. Note that the density increase from 11% to 18% corresponded to peak strength, valley strength, and elastic modulus increases of 105%, 140%, and 135%, respectively (values summarized

Table 1. Compressive properties for the low density and high density stochastic honeycombs.

Sample	Peak Strength (MPa)	Valley Strength (MPa)	Elastic Modulus (MPa)
LD	2.23	0.92	59
HD	4.61	2.23	139

Fig. 7. As-fabricated LD web bounded on each side (a), and the vertical tear created by the horizontal tensile strain from the compression of the bounding webs (b). The scale bar is 2 mm and applies to both figures.

in Table 1). Classification of the web failure mechanisms was based on the web end constraint conditions. The complete webs that were bounded on both sides tended to tear vertically, as seen in Fig. 7, from the LD sample. This study focuses on the webs that are bounded on one side and free on the other. Six webs from each sample were analyzed for their dimensions and failure mechanisms, termed LD-1 to LD-6, and HD-1 to HD-6. Four specific examples are presented below (LD-1, LD-2, HD-1, and HD-2), with general results of the overall analysis discussed afterwards.

The web (LD-1) shown in Fig. 8 is from the low density sample. Two views are shown of the as-fabricated (Fig. 8a and 8b) and partially compressed (Fig. 8d and 8e) webs, while Fig. 8c and 8f show cross-sections along the height (through-thickness) of the sandwich. Fig. 9 plots the thickness of the web (x -axis) against the normalized position through the height (y -axis), giving a thickness profile of the web, also shown in cross-section. The dashed line indicates the point of buckling failure. The web

Fig. 8. LD-1 as-fabricated from the side (a), straight on (b), in vertical cross-section (c), and partially compressed from the side (d), straight on (e), and in vertical cross-section (f). The scale bar is 2.5 mm and applies to all the figures.

Fig. 9. Thickness profile of LD-1 and the vertical cross-section for comparison. The dashed line marks the point of initiation of instability.

Table 2. LD-1 dimensions at failure initiation point.

Position, h	Thickness, t (mm)	Aspect Ratio, t/l
0.52	0.15	0.104

Fig. 10. LD-2 as-fabricated from the side (a), straight on (b), in vertical cross-section (c), and partially compressed from the side (d), straight on (e), and in vertical cross-section (f). The scale bar is 2.5 mm and applies to all the figures.

Fig. 11. Thickness profile of LD-2 and the vertical cross-section for comparison. The dashed lines mark the locations of initiation of instability.

Table 3. LD-2 dimensions at failure initiation points.

Position, h	Thickness, t (mm)	Aspect Ratio, t/l
0.11	0.29	0.103
0.70	0.32	0.189
0.89	0.31	0.152

Fig. 12. HD-1 as-fabricated from the side (a), straight on (b), in vertical cross-section (c), and partially compressed from the side (d), straight on (e), and in vertical cross-section (f). The scale bar is 2.5 mm and applies to all the figures.

Fig. 13. Thickness profile of HD-1 and the vertical cross-section for comparison. The dashed line marks the location of initiation of instability.

Table 4. HD-1 dimensions at failure initiation point.

Position, h	Thickness, t (mm)	Aspect Ratio, t/l
0.42	0.21	0.042

Fig. 14. HD-2 as-fabricated from the side (a), from the opposite side (b), straight on (c), in vertical cross-section (d), and partially compressed from the side (e), from the opposite side (f), straight on (g), and in vertical cross-section (h). The scale bar is 2.5 mm and applies to all the figures.

Fig. 15. HD-2 buttress as-fabricated (a), in vertical cross-section (b), and partially compressed (c), in vertical cross-section (d). The scale bar is 1 mm and applies to all the figures.

Table 5. HD-2 dimensions at failure initiation points.

Position, h	Thickness, t (mm)	Aspect Ratio, t/l
0.72	0.50	0.125
0.82	0.31	0.345
0.90	0.46	0.123

Fig. 16. Thickness profile of HD-2 and the buttress (inset) with vertical cross-sections for comparison. The dashed lines mark the locations of initiation of instability.

thickness was ~ 0.2 mm and ~ 0.4 mm at the top and bottom (respectively) of the sample and 0.15 mm in the centre. This web did not buckle at the thinnest point, but rather just above the mid-point along the height dimension. From Fig. 8c, the cross-section of the as-fabricated web shows that there is already some slight curvature in the area where the web buckled, so while LD-1 did not buckle at the thinnest point, it did buckle at the area just above the thinnest point where some curvature was already present. The thickness/length aspect ratio of this web was $t/l = 0.10$ (Table 2).

Another web (LD-2) from the same sample is shown in Fig. 10. This web undergoes a somewhat more complex failure mechanism, with both web buckling and web fracture being seen in the post-loaded scan. Fig. 10b and 10c show that the web has some curvature before compression, and afterwards, in addition to the tear, LD-2 buckled at the bottom ($h = 0.11$) and the top ($h = 0.89$). Unlike LD-1, this web was thinner near the top and bottom (where buckling occurred). The pre-compression curvature leads to increased bending strains at the thinnest regions, causing the upper and lower buckles, and then the tear just below the upper buckle. From the thickness profile (Fig. 11), the web tears at $t = 0.32$ mm, where the aspect ratio is 0.189. The two buckles occur where the web is 0.29 mm and 0.31 mm thick, and the aspect ratios are 0.103 and 0.152, for the bottom and top, respectively (Table 3).

The web shown in Fig. 12, in contrast, is from the high-density sample (HD-1). Similarly to LD-1, it is bound on one side and free on the other. As Fig. 12b

and 12c show, this web had some curvature to begin with, and buckled in the centre in the direction of the initial curvature. At the buckle, this web is at its thinnest point ($t = 0.21$ mm, Table 4) as seen in the thickness profile in Fig. 13. The thickness at the top and bottom of this web is ~ 0.4 mm, so its thinnest point is only 50% of its maximum thickness. This web had a thick supporting web, as seen straight-on in Fig. 12a. The supporting web buckled at the top and tore, as seen in Fig. 12d. HD-1 is thicker than LD-1 (0.21 mm compared to 0.15 mm), but has a lower aspect ratio because it spans a longer distance. This is typical of the HD sample; it had thicker webs, as can be seen from Fig. 2, but the webs are also longer, leading to lower aspect ratios overall.

HD-2, shown in Fig. 14, is another web from the high-density sample. In addition to being supported on one side, it is supported by a buttress at the top, which is visible in Fig. 14b and on the opposite side of the view shown in Fig. 14a. While this web has little initial curvature, it is tilted to one side, as can be seen in Fig. 14c and 14d. After compression, this web has buckled near the top ($t = 0.46$ mm, Table 5) and torn a short distance below the buckle. The buttress supplies extra support for this web, and tears itself, as can be seen in Fig. 15. The thickness profile for HD-2 (Fig. 16) shows that the buckle occurs at the thinnest point of the web, and the tear occurs at the upper end of the buttress (Fig. 15c). The thickness profile for the buttress, shown in the inset for Fig. 16, demonstrates that the buttress also tore near its thinnest point, stressed by the buckle of the web it was supporting. This web tore near a buckle, as the LD-2 web did. HD-2 had $t = 0.50$ mm at the tear, while LD-2 had $t = 0.32$ mm. Even though HD-2 was 50% thicker than LD-2, it has a lower aspect ratio (0.125 for HD-2 and 0.189 for LD-2). Again, this is due to the longer webs in the HD sample compared to the LD sample.

Table 6 summarizes the thickness and aspect ratio data at failure for all of the webs considered in this first study. As some webs had multiple failures, these are each separately recorded in the table. The table is sorted by aspect ratio (t/l), and the failure mechanism at each failure is recorded as well. Critical buckling stress for a thin wall, first developed by Bryan in 1890 [16] is a function of the aspect ratio, t/l , squared. A slender web, with a low aspect ratio, will have a lower critical buckling

Table 6. Thickness and aspect ratio correlated with failure mechanism

Web	Thickness (mm)	Aspect Ratio (t/l)	Failure Mechanism
HD-1	0.21	0.042	buckle
LD-3	0.18	0.054	buckle
LD-3	0.19	0.058	buckle
HD-4	0.39	0.076	buckle
HD-4	0.32	0.095	buckle
LD-1	0.15	0.103	buckle
LD-2	0.29	0.103	buckle
HD-4	0.30	0.103	buckle
LD-5	0.35	0.115	tear
HD-3	0.57	0.119	buckle
HD-2	0.46	0.123	buckle
HD-2	0.50	0.125	buckle
LD-4	0.60	0.128	tear
LD-4	0.61	0.128	buckle/tear
HD-5	0.93	0.145	tear
LD-2	0.31	0.152	buckle
LD-5	0.38	0.161	buckle
LD-2	0.32	0.189	tear
LD-5	0.45	0.217	tear
LD-4	0.51	0.250	tear
HD-2	0.31	0.345	tear

stress. A web with a higher aspect ratio will hold more stress, until reaching either its critical buckling stress or the local fracture strength of the material. From the table, it is clear that if the aspect ratio is greater than 0.17, the web will fail by tearing. Conversely, if the aspect ratio is less than 0.11, the web will fail by buckling only. Between these values, the web will either tear or buckle depending on the local environment and geometry. For example, LD-2 with an aspect ratio of 0.152 buckled above a tear, so the web's constraints had radically changed before that buckle occurred. Critical buckling stress is also a function of the end constraints, which depend in part on the vertical aspect ratio of the webs, h/l .

4 Conclusions

The strength and stiffness of stochastic honeycombs are determined by the complex internal architecture of the webs. Micro-CT scans were used to track the detailed local failure mechanisms within the core of the sandwich structure for 'low' (11%) and 'high' (18%) relative density variants. Post failure micro-CT characterization showed that web buckling and web fracture were seen in both sample types. Web buckling tended to occur at the thinnest portions of

the web, whether this was at mid-height or not. The subset of partially constrained webs (i.e. those supported on one side and free on the other) could be classified into one of two failure modes: web buckle only and web buckle plus web fracture. Webs with a thickness-to-length aspect ratio of $t/l < 0.11$ tended to buckle only, while higher aspect ratio webs would both buckle and fracture ($t/l > 0.18$).

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